

FIBRE-COMPOSITE REINFORCEMENT OF CRACKED AIRCRAFT STRUCTURES -

THERMAL-STRESS AND THERMAL-FATIGUE STUDIES

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Summary

Boron fibre reinforced plastics have been used successfully at ARL, Australia, to repair fatigue or stress-corrosion cracked metallic aerospace components. However, problems in the use of this repair technique can occur, in certain circumstances, due to the tensile residual stresses which arise in the metal component, caused by the mismatch in thermal expansion coefficients between the fibre composite and the metal.

This paper describes i) studies using X-ray diffraction procedures, to determine the stress distributions in cracked and uncracked reinforced 7075T6 aluminium specimens (carbon-fibre reinforced plastics were used as the reinforcement to allow X-ray penetration to the metal surface), and ii) experiments to establish the resistance of the epoxy-nitrile adhesive layer to damage, in boron fibre reinforced aluminium alloy specimens, when subjected to thermal cycling.

Introduction

Work on advanced fibre composites and adhesives at the Aeronautical Research Laboratories has resulted in the development of a new method for repairing fatigue or stress-corrosion cracked metallic structures, based on the use of adhesively-bonded boron fibre reinforced plastic (BFRP) patches⁽¹⁾. This procedure has advantages over standard repair procedures which are usually based on mechanically-attached metallic patches; table I sets out some of the advantages of the BFRP repair scheme when compared with the standard procedure.

The BFRP repair has been successfully applied to i) stress-corrosion cracks in the wing planks of Hercules transport aircraft, ii) fatigue cracks in the landing wheels of Macchi aircraft, and iii) fatigue cracks in the wing and fuselage of a Nomad test aircraft. Examples of these repairs are shown in Figs. 1a, 2 and 3 with relevant details. Fig. 1b shows a standard Hercules repair; because of the relative complexity of this repair, only cracks > 200 mm are usually repaired by this procedure. The Hercules and Macchi repairs have been accepted as standard by the RAAF; all future repairs, of the type described, will be carried out by RAAF personnel in the case of the Hercules, and by Dunlop Aviation, Australia

Fig. 1a. General view of the underside of an upper Hercules wing plank (aluminium alloy, 7075T6), showing examples of BFRP repair patches adhesively bonded over stress-corrosion cracks, which initiate from rivet holes at the points of connection with the rib. The cracks are about 50 mm long. Repairs have been in service for about 3 years in a number of aircraft with no evidence of further crack propagation.

Fig. 1b. Similar view to Figure 1a showing an example of the standard repair scheme, based on a mechanically-fastened metal repair patch, applied to a 250 mm crack.

Fig. 2. Macchi landing wheel (magnesium alloy, MSR) showing BFRP repair patches bonded over the ends of a fatigue crack about 20 mm long. This wheel has made about 1000 landings since the repair; without the repair, crack growth would have made the wheel unserviceable after about 30 further landings.

Fig. 3. Nomad fatigue test aircraft showing a BFRP patch bonded over a fatigue crack caused by 'oil-can' deformation of the skin. No further growth of the fatigue crack has occurred after the equivalent of over 20,000 hours flying time.

in the case of the Macchi. A number of other BFRP repairs are under investigation and could be introduced in due course.

Standard Repairs	ARL Bonded BFRP Repairs
Severe stress concentration at points of attachment	No severe stress concentration
Limited fatigue strength of patch	Fatigue resistant patch
Relatively thick patch	Thin patch (1/3 x thickness Al patch 1/5 x thickness Mg patch)
Curved patches costly to produce	Simple inexpensive moulding technique
Cracks cannot easily be monitored through patch	Usually no NDI problems
Electrochemical properties of metal must match structure to avoid corrosion problems	No corrosion problems even with Mg
Crevice corrosion may develop under patch	Sealed interface
	Minimises out of balance in rotating parts
	No transverse reinforcement unless required

Table 1. Advantages of bonded BFRP repairs over standard mechanical repairs

Successful application of the crack-patching technique depends on the ability of the adhesive system to transfer load from the cracked component to the patch under normal stress and operating conditions. Two properties of the adhesive system which are of particular importance are its fatigue strength and resistance to stress relaxation. Thus, initial background work determined the fatigue and relaxation characteristics of a number of adhesives when used to bond BFRP to 7075T6 aluminium alloy(2). Selection of the adhesive is complicated by:

- i) the need to avoid chemical pre-treatments of the surface to improve bonding to the cracked component (because of the danger of stress corrosion), and
- ii) the desirability of a low curing temperature to avoid thermally induced tensile stresses in the cracked component, resulting from the relatively low thermal expansion coefficient of BFRP in the fibre direction

Only one of the adhesives studied gave acceptable fatigue and stress-relaxation properties with the use of a simple, non-chemical bonding pre-treatment. This adhesive was the epoxy nitrile AF126; the only bonding pre-treatment required for both the aluminium surface and the patch was a solvent degrease, then an alumina grit-blasting, followed by a final solvent clean.

Unfortunately, AF126 must be cured at approximately 120°C (under pressure), leading to fairly high levels of tensile stress in the metal component when cooled to room temperature. It was considered that the residual stress in the cracked component may encourage the growth of the crack by stress corrosion. To evaluate this possibility, stress-corrosion experiments were carried out using wedge-loaded 7075T6 specimens containing active stress-corrosion cracks; the material, specimen/width and patch size were those used in the Hercules repair. Fig. 4 shows that, despite the thermal stress, patching with BFRP either prevents, or very substantially reduces, all further crack growth. Although these experiments showed that, at least in the situation studied, thermal stresses do not hinder the crack-stopping ability of the patch, it is possible that stress-corrosion cracking problems, due to thermal stress, could arise in other situations. A more detailed study was therefore undertaken of the effect of reinforcement with fibre composite on cracked metal specimens. Part 1 of this paper describes some initial work in this area, using X-ray diffraction to determine stress distribution in cracked and reinforced aluminium alloy panels.

Thermal fatigue is another potential problem in the adhesive layer; even during normal operations in a subsonic aircraft, it is possible for temperature fluctuations from -50°C to +100°C to occur, resulting in shear-stress cycling and possibly fatigue cracking of the adhesive. Studies of the significance of this effect on BFRP-reinforced aluminium alloy specimens are described in Part 2 of this paper.

Fig. 4. Plots of crack growth versus time for wedge-loaded 7075T6 aluminium alloy stress-corrosion specimens reinforced with the crack tip centrally under the patches; taken from reference 1.

The mismatch in coefficients of thermal expansion between the metal component and the reinforcement also results in residual shear stresses in the adhesive layer. Environmental effects, mainly due to moisture, can result in failure of the adhesive bond under long-term exposure conditions; the magnitude of the effect of environment is being studied and will be described elsewhere.

Part 1. Thermal Stress Studies

1.1 Experimental Procedure

Residual thermal stresses were measured, using an X-ray back-reflection procedure⁽³⁾, on aluminium alloy (7075T6) sheet specimens reinforced with CFRP strips adhesively bonded to both surfaces. BFRP was our main interest in the crack-repair work, but it prevents X-ray penetration to the metal surface and so could not be used for these measurements. The CFRP and the adhesive layer did not contribute to the back-reflection diffraction pattern from the metal surface. The two types of reinforced aluminium alloy specimens evaluated were a) with a plain metal core 115 mm x 25 mm x 1.56 mm, and b) with a center crack in the metal core, of dimensions 112 mm x 112 mm x 1.56 mm and crack lengths 5, 15 and 30 mm. The CFRP reinforcing strips were approximately 0.49 mm thick (made from 3 layers of pre-preg material) and were bonded to the aluminium alloy sheet using an epoxy-nitrile film adhesive with the fibres aligned in the 115 mm direction in type (a) specimens and normally to the crack in type (b) specimens; table II gives details of the reinforcement and table III, details of the adhesive and bonding conditions. The simulated cracks in the aluminium alloy specimens were produced by spark machining using a 0.2 mm thick brass sheet as the electrode; the resulting slots had tip radii of about 0.2 mm.

The X-ray stress measurement procedure consisted of a multi-exposure, back-reflection film technique; the stress was computed from the slope of a $\text{cosec } \theta / \sin^2 \psi$ plot, where the symbols have their usual meaning in X-ray diffraction terminology. The measurements were carried out, at selected spots in the specimens, using pinhole collimation of the X-ray beam. A beam diameter at the specimen of about 1.75 mm was used for examining the plain specimen but, for work on the cracked specimens, a beam diameter of just over 1 mm was used. It should be noted that the reported stresses are an average over these diameters. Very accurate positioning of the X-ray beam was possible when measurements were made on the artificially cracked specimens since the X-ray beam could be used to produce a radiograph, which showed its location relative to the hidden crack, prior to recording the diffraction data.

1.2 Experimental Results and Discussion

1.2.1 CFRP Reinforced (Un-cracked) Specimens

Measurements of the stress, parallel to the fibres in the reinforced specimens at various points along the central axis of the specimen are plotted in Fig. 5a. Fig. 5a also shows the estimated initial mean stress in the unreinforced aluminium and the 95% confidence limits for the mean and individual measurements.

A simple model was used to provide a theoretical estimate of the stress distribution in the metal core of the reinforced specimens for comparison with the experimental results. This model, (Fig. 6a and b) assumes that the thermal stress distributions in the reinforcing strip $\sigma_s^T(x)$ and the metal component $\sigma_p^T(x)$ are the sums of a) constant stresses σ_s and σ_p , respectively, which are equal to the thermal stress which would arise if the metal and composite were rigidly connected, and b), varying stresses,

Composite	Matrix and curing conditions	Comments
CFRP	Epoxy, Shell 828/DDS. Held under pressure of 1.38 MPa for 16 minutes at 150°C. Temperature raised to 180°C for 2 hours. Post cure at 200°C for 2 hours.	Supplied as sized warp sheet by Hyfil Ltd., UK.
BFRP	Epoxy, PR-286 (3M Company, USA) 2 hours at 150°C 2 hours at 180°C 4 hours at 200°C Pressure 689 KPa	Supplied as a pre-preg tape, (with fibres held on a glass cloth) by Composite Materials Corporation, USA.

Table II. Details of the CFRP and BFRP reinforcements used.

Adhesive	Bonding Conditions	Substrate bonding pre-treatment	
		Composite	Aluminium alloy 7075T6
AFl26 epoxy-nitrile film* with Dacron-fibre carrier. Initial film thickness ~ 0.18 mm.	Pressed at 340KPa for 1 hour at 126°C.	(a) MEK degrease. (b) Alumina grit blast; 50 µm grit, (light blast - no fibres exposed). (c) MEK wipe. Laboratory grade solvent.	X-ray stress-analysis specimens abraded on 600 grade paper in place of grit blast. Thermal-fatigue specimens as per composite but with saturation grit blast.
*Supplied by 3M Company, USA			

Table III. Details of adhesive-bonding conditions and substrate pre-treatments for bonding used.

$\sigma_s(x)$ and $\sigma_p(x)$ respectively, due to virtual stresses $-\sigma_s$ and $-\sigma_p$ acting on the reinforcing strip and metal component respectively, at $\pm L/2$. It is assumed, initially, that no shear deformation occurs in the metal or the reinforcing layer.

Thus:

$$\sigma_p^T(x) = \sigma_p + \sigma_p(x)$$

$$\sigma_s^T(x) = \sigma_s + \sigma_s(x)$$

Fig. 5a. Plot of measured stress, at various points along the aluminium core of the reinforced specimens, versus distance x measured along the central axis of the specimens; the stresses measured are in the x direction (parallel to the fibres).

Fig. 5b. Plot of stress $\sigma_p^T(x)$ versus distance x along the aluminium core of the reinforced specimens; the stress $\sigma_p^T(x)$ was calculated from equation 1 using the values for constants listed in table IV.

Fig. 6. a) Arrangement of reinforcing layer and metal component around center line.
 b) Elemental model assumed in estimating thermal stress distribution.

The stress distribution in the metal component is then given (Appendix 1) by

$$\sigma_p^T(x) = \sigma_p \left(1 - \frac{\sinh ax}{\sinh(aL/2)} \right) \quad 1)$$

and the corresponding equation for the shear stress in the adhesive layer $\tau(x)$ is (Appendix 1),

$$\tau(x) = \frac{\sigma_p da \cosh ax}{2 \sinh(aL/2)} \left[\text{at } x = \pm \frac{L}{2}, \tau(x) \approx \sigma_p \frac{da}{2} \right] \quad 2)$$

where

$$a = \sqrt{\frac{G_L}{t_L} \left(\frac{1}{t_s E_s} + \frac{2}{d E_p} \right)} \quad 3)$$

and

$$\sigma_p = \frac{2 t_s E_p E_s \Delta T \Delta \alpha}{d E_p + 2 t_s E_s}$$

where ΔT is the temperature difference between the cure temperature and the measurement temperature (approximately 100°C) and $\Delta \alpha$ the difference in thermal expansion coefficient between the metal and the reinforcement.

Fig. 5b plots $\sigma_p^T(x)$ versus distance, x , using the constants and dimensions listed in table IV. Curves for two values of adhesive shear modulus, G_L , are plotted, viz, a) 0.7 MPa, as obtained from torsion pendulum measurements, and b) 0.5 MPa, an assumed effective value after full stress relaxation. Comparison with Fig. 5a shows that both of the theoretical curves in Fig. 5b predict a more rapid fall-off in stress closer to the ends of the reinforced specimen than was observed; however, overall agreement between theory and experiment, assuming $G_L = 0.5$ MPa, seems fairly reasonable if allowance is made for experimental scatter.

Material	Modulus GPa	Shear Modulus GPa	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion $\times 10^{-6}$	Thickness mm
Aluminium alloy 7075T6	72	27	23	1.56 (a) (b) and (c)
CFRP	130	7	0.5	0.49 (a) and (b)
BFRP	192	10	5	0.41 (c)
Adhesive AF126	-	0.7 (20°C) 0.8 (-10°C) 1.0 (-50°C) 1.3 (-100°C)	-	0.15 (a) 0.10 (c)

- (a) reinforced specimens for thermal-stress measurements;
- (b) artificially cracked reinforced specimens;
- (c) reinforced specimens subject to thermal fatigue.

Table IV. Values of constants and dimensions for the materials used in thermal-stress and thermal-fatigue experiments

One major assumption made in the theoretical model is that both the metal component and the composite suffer no shear deformation. While this assumption is reasonable for the metal, it is rather inappropriate for the composite layer which has a fairly low shear modulus, (table IV).

However, consideration of the stress variation in the y direction (Fig. 6a) through the thickness of the composite, complicates the analysis. Previous considerations⁽²⁾, assuming an average shear stress of half that in the adhesive layer, suggest that, at least to a first approximation, allowance for shear deformation can be made by replacing the ratio t_L/G_L in equation 3 with $(t_L/4G + t_L/G_L)$, where G_L is the shear modulus of the composite given in table IV. This correction is quite significant for small t_L or large G_L ; however, for the assumed t_L and G_L , it is not significant and cannot explain differences between experiment and theory.

1.2.2 CFRP - Reinforced Cracked Specimens - Preliminary Studies

Only one specimen, that having the 15 mm central crack, has been analysed in detail at this stage. Figs. 7a and 7b show the results of stress measurements, σ_{yy} , in the fibre direction, as a function of distance, y, from the crack surface, for this specimen. Fig. 8a plots the results of stress measurement, σ_{yy} , as a function of distance, r, from the crack tip (measured on the axis of the crack), for specimens with the 5 mm, 15 mm and 30 mm cracks.

Fig. 7b shows that the stress, although falling (as expected) as the edge of the crack is approached along the y direction from the center of the crack, suddenly increases near the edge of the crack. This rise is attributed to local melting and freezing during the spark-machining causing local stresses, which can be ignored for the present purposes. When the region of elevated stress is ignored the stress distribution in the cracked specimen agrees quite well with the uncracked specimens (Figs. 5a and b), if the end of the specimen is equated with the crack. Unfortunately detailed comparison is difficult because of the scatter in results in the cracked specimens; this arises because of the need to use a small diameter X-ray beam in these measurements.

The apparent stress intensity, K, produced by the thermal stress can be estimated from the results of Fig. 8a for the various cracked specimens by using the relationship for a blunt crack⁽⁴⁾, assumed valid for the reinforced specimens,

$$\sigma_{yy} = \frac{K}{\sqrt{2\pi r}} \cdot \frac{1 + \rho/r}{(1 + \rho/2r)^{3/2}}$$

where r is the distance along the axis of the crack from the crack tip and ρ is the radius of curvature at the crack tip. This expression is valid (for situations in which it applies) only at points very close to the crack tip, as $r \rightarrow 0$. Fig. 8b plots values of K versus r, based on data from Fig. 8a and the above equation. The value of K as $r \rightarrow 0$ is obtained by assuming that the plots in Fig. 8b can be linearly extrapolated to $r = 0$. The extrapolated values of K are, respectively, 9 MPa \sqrt{m} (5 mm crack), 13 MPa \sqrt{m} (15 mm crack) and 19 MPa \sqrt{m} (30 mm crack); these values are in the ratios 1:1.4:2.1. If K were proportional to the square root of crack length, as is usual in many cases, then the expected ratios would be 1:1.7:2.5, agreeing quite well with the experimental values. However, the actual values of K are quite high and the above interpretation is open to question, particularly when applied to a growing crack, for three reasons: i) The reinforcement prevented further crack propagation in stress-corrosion experiments on wedge-loaded specimens with active cracks⁽¹⁾ (Fig. 4), although the above figures for K are well above the stress-corrosion threshold for 7075T6 aluminium. ii) If the stress field had been typical of that normally associated with a given value of K close to the crack, σ_{xx} (the stress in the metal normal to the fibre direction) should have been of the same order as σ_{yy} . However, X-ray stress measurements made in line with the axis of the crack, 5 mm from the crack tip, in the specimen with the 15 mm crack gave a value for σ_{xx} close to zero. iii) Finally, theoretical considerations suggest that the stress intensity should be independent of

Fig. 7a. and b. Plots of stress (σ_{yy}) versus distance from axis of the crack (y) for the 15 mm crack.

Fig. 8a. Plot of stress (σ_{yy} in the fibre direction) versus distance from the crack tip (r) measured along the axis of the crack.

Fig. 8b. Plot of apparent stress intensity K , estimated from the above plots, versus distance from the crack tip (r) measured along the axis of the crack.

crack length. These considerations are based on the assumption that the energy or driving force for extension of the crack is derived from the loss in strain energy in the metal around the crack as the crack propagates. It is assumed that the composite reinforcement in the region of the crack maintains its compressive stress because of support from the neighbouring composite in uncracked regions; this is equivalent to assuming that the boundaries of the reinforced plate undergo no displacement after the formation of the crack. On this basis the rate of strain energy loss, per unit of crack extension G is given by

$$G \approx 2 d \sigma_p^2 / a E_p$$

which is independent of crack length and quite small in magnitude. The expression for G is obtained by finding the strain energy in the metal component after formation of a crack, width $2c$, using equation 1, and differentiating with respect to c . The validity of using equation 1 to obtain an expression for G is demonstrated by the reasonable agreement between Fig. 7b, for the stress distribution in the cracked specimen and Figs. 5a and b, for the uncracked specimen.

Further studies are planned, using the X-ray technique on reinforced panels containing active stress-corrosion cracks to resolve the situation regarding the effective stress intensity.

Part 2. Thermal Fatigue Studies

2.1 Experimental Details

BFRP reinforced aluminium alloy 7075T6 specimens of sandwich construction were used in the thermal fatigue tests. BFRP strips 0.4 mm thick (made from 3 layers of pre-preg tape) were bonded to each side of aluminium alloy coupons approximately 75 mm x 10 mm, 1.6 mm thick, with the fibres aligned in the 75 mm direction; the bonding conditions are given in table III. In addition BFRP and CFRP specimens 75 mm x 10 mm x 2 mm, with the fibres aligned in the 75 mm direction, were subjected to thermal fatigue and temperature exposure for comparison with the reinforced specimens.

The thermal-cycling apparatus, (Fig. 9) consists of rotating steel arms to which specimens are attached by light stainless steel frames. The arms pass alternately through an electrically-heated zone and a cooled zone; the cooling is produced as the specimens pass between a pair of stainless-steel tanks filled with liquid nitrogen. The desired thermal cycling was obtained by adjusting the temperature of the heated zone and the cycling period of the rotating arms. Temperatures were measured with an iron/constantan thermocouple, inserted into a central hole in one of the sandwich specimens and were plotted, as a function of time, on a recorder; Fig. 10 plots a typical thermal cycle. Preliminary tests, with the thermocouple in various positions in a sandwich specimen, had shown that all parts of the specimen underwent the same thermal cycle, with only slight phase differences longitudinally.

Three series of tests were carried out as indicated in Table V. Cycling was not continuous but was carried out daily because of the need to replenish the liquid nitrogen tanks regularly. Specimens were examined by an eddy-current NDI procedure initially and then after 200 and 500 cycles and at the completion of each series. The eddy-current technique measures the distance of lift-off of the probe from the metal surface under the composite reinforcement and, therefore, gives an indication of any gross debonding of the reinforcing layer. Some specimens were removed for metallographic examination of transverse taper sections at completion.

Fig. 9. Schematic diagram of the thermal-cycling rig.

Fig. 10. Thermal cycle for Series 3 specimens.

of series 1 and 2, but most specimens underwent the complete three series of tests prior to final metallographic examination. CFRP and BFRP specimens were examined by ultrasonic C-Scan techniques for evidence of debonding after thermal cycling and were then mechanically tested to determine changes in interlaminar shear strength. For the interlaminar shear tests, five test pieces 12 mm x 10 mm were cut from each of the cycled specimen.

Series	Upper Temperature ±2°C	Lower Temperature ±2°C	No. of cycles (approx)	cycle period min.	approx. max shear stress in adhesive. MPa
1	120	-10	1040	6	38
2	120	-50	1120	9	55
3	120	-104	800	12	82

Table V. Details of thermal-fatigue tests

2.2 Experimental Results and Discussion

The NDI tests revealed no evidence of gross cracking in the reinforced aluminium alloy specimens after thermal cycling. However, the sensitivity of the NDI test to thermal cracking was demonstrated on a group of specimens which had been accidentally overheated (to approximately 290°C for 30 minutes) during early trials of the thermal-cycling apparatus. Prior to overheating, these specimens had shown no cracking after thermal cycling; however, subsequent to overheating, considerable cracking was detected after a further similar period of cycling. As expected, cracking occurred only in the zone of high shear stress at each end of the specimen.

Metallographic examination of thermally cycled specimens did not reveal any damage in series 1 and 2 specimens, table V. However, some micro-cracking was found in series 3 specimens which had been exposed to the most severe cycling conditions, table V. Fig. 11 shows that micro-cracking occurs a) within the adhesive layer, usually linking voids and associated with the Dacron carrier fibres, b) along the aluminium/adhesive interface, linked with cracks in the adhesive layer and c) within the matrix of the BFRP reinforcing layer, close to the reinforcement/adhesive interface. Micro-cracking of this nature would not be detected by the NDI technique, which would detect only fairly extensive cracking or debonding.

Since there was no marked tendency for the micro-cracking to occur at the aluminium/adhesive interface, it is concluded that the non-chemical method of bonding pre-treatment used for the aluminium (listed in table III) is adequate for this adhesive under conditions of thermal fatigue. A similar conclusion, regarding this bonding pre-treatment, was also reached from ambient temperature static⁽⁵⁾ and fatigue tests⁽²⁾. However, bonds prepared by the non-chemical pre-treatment are not expected to resist moisture or other environmental agents as well as those prepared by the standard chemical procedures.

The peak shear stress in the thermal fatigue test is encountered during the cold part of the thermal cycle and the minimum shear stress during the

hot part; since the maximum temperature coincides with the cure temperature, the minimum stress should be zero. Estimates of the peak shear stresses (table V) were obtained using equation 2, section 1.2 for $\tau(x)$ max, with values for the material constants and dimensions taken from table IV. The reasonable correlation obtained between the corresponding equation for stress in the metal component (equation 1, section 1.2 and the experimental values for the CFRP reinforced specimens, give at least limited confidence in the use of equation 2 to predict peak shear stress in the thermal fatigue experiments.

Some idea of the thermal cycling conditions which are safe and those which result in some damage to the adhesive layer may be obtained from the above experiments. These results may, at least tentatively, be applied to other specimen geometries and thermal cycles. However, much more thermal fatigue testing, including environmental variables, such as moisture, will be needed to define clearly the limitations imposed by thermal cycling.

Tables VIa and b list the interlaminar shear (ILS) test results on the basis of the ratio ILS test specimen/ILS reference specimen for the fibre composites and show that some specimens appear to be strengthened by thermal cycling and that none are significantly weakened; the BFRP results, table VIa show the strengthening effect most clearly. Since prolonged heating at the maximum cycle temperature also produces a significant improvement in ILS of the BFRP specimens but prolonged cooling does not (table VIa), it is concluded that the observed thermal-cycling result is, at least partially, due to post-curing during the hot part of the cycle. Thermal cycling also appears to result in a slight improvement in the ILS of the CFRP specimens (table VIb). However, no significant improvement with prolonged heating could be obtained in CFRP specimens. As expected from these thermal-cycling results, metallographic examination of the BFRP and CFRP specimens failed to reveal any cracking.

Fig. 11 Micrograph of a section through the end of a BFRP reinforced aluminium alloy specimen, after thermal fatigue to series 3 conditions, table V, showing microcracking in the adhesive layer, at the aluminium/adhesive interface and in the matrix of the BFRP. Fibre diameter $100\mu\text{m}$.

Treatment	ILS Ratio to reference specimen (a)	Sample Standard Deviation 5×10^2 (b)	Significance (c)
Reference specimens	1.0	2.80	-
1040 cycles -10°/120°C	1.026	4.30	not significant
250 cycles -50°/120°C	1.143	3.98	highly significant
800 cycles -104°/120°C	1.093	2.05	highly significant
heated 120°C, 33 hours	1.141	1.03	highly significant
cooled -160°C, 33 hours	1.016	3.49	not significant

(a) Reference ILS is approximately 76 MPa for BFRP. b) Based on 5 specimens of each type. c) Based on Student's t test for difference in mean ratio to reference specimen.

Table VIa. Results of ILS tests after thermal cycling and thermal treatments of BFRP specimens.

Treatment	ILS Ratio (a)	Sample Standard Deviation (b)	Significance (c)
Reference Specimens	1.0	2.76	-
1040 cycles -10°/120°C	1.020	2.00	not significant
1040 cycles -10°/120°C + 1120 cycles -50°/120°C	1.055	2.33	significant
1120 cycles -50°/120°C	1.047	1.79	significant
800 cycles -104/120°C	0.975	1.29	not significant
heated 120°C, 33 hours	1.026	2.48	not significant
cooled -160°C 33 hours	0.987	0.6	not significant

Notes; (b) and (c) see Table VIa. (a) Reference ILS is 79 MPa for CFRP

Table VIb. Results of ILS tests after thermal cycling and thermal treatments of CFRP specimens

Conclusions

1. X-ray stress measurements on 7075T6 aluminium panels reinforced with layers of CFRP have shown that a simple analytical expression can be used to predict the residual stress distribution in the metal component and, therefore, the residual shear stress in the adhesive layer.
2. X-ray stress measurements have also shown the residual stress distribution around simulated cracks in the metal component of the reinforced panel. These stresses have been interpreted in terms of an apparent stress intensity by linear plotting of the X-ray data. However, relatively high values of stress intensity are predicted by this procedure which are not consistent with previous experimental observations on the growth of stress-corrosion cracks in reinforced specimens and may require interpretation in the context of a growing crack.
3. Thermal-fatigue studies on BFRP - reinforced 7075T6 aluminium specimens have shown that the epoxy-nitrile adhesive used was able to withstand over a thousand cycles from +120°C to -50°C without damage, despite the simple non-chemical pre-bonding treatments used on the metal and composite surfaces. However, some small scale microcracking occurred in cycling from +120°C to -100°C.
4. CFRP and BFRP specimens, with unidirectional fibre orientation, subjected to thermal cycling, from +120°C to -100°C, showed a slight but significant improvement in interlaminar shear strength. This improvement, in the case of BFRP, was attributed to post-curing during the elevated temperature portion of the thermal cycle.

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Appendix 1, Thermal Stress Calculations

Considering initially only the element in Fig. 6b with varying stresses:

i) Equilibrium of Stresses Considerations of equilibrium

$$\text{gives } \sigma_p(x)d/2 = -\sigma_s(x)t_s$$

$$\text{and } \tau(x) = \frac{d}{2} \cdot \frac{d\sigma_p(x)}{dx}$$

ii) Compatibility of Deformations Consideration of displacements through the adhesive

$$\text{gives } u_s = u_p + t_L \delta$$

, where u_s and u_p are the displacements in the reinforcing strip and metal

$$\text{and since } \frac{du_s}{dx} = \frac{\sigma_s(x)}{E_s}, \quad \frac{du_p}{dx} = \frac{\sigma_p(x)}{E_p} \quad \text{and} \quad \delta = \frac{\tau(x)}{G_L}$$

, where E_s and E_p are the elastic moduli of the reinforcing strip and metal and G_L the shear modulus of the adhesive, we have that:

$$\frac{\sigma_s(x)}{E_s} = \frac{\sigma_p(x)}{E_p} + \frac{t_L}{G_L} \frac{d\tau(x)}{dx}$$

substituting for $\tau(x)$ and $\sigma_s(x)$ from the stress equilibrium conditions

$$\text{gives } \frac{d^2\sigma_p(x)}{dx^2} - \sigma_p(x) \left(\frac{G_L}{t_s t_L E_s} + \frac{2G_L}{t_L d E_p} \right) = 0$$

which has the solution

$$\sigma_p(x) = \frac{b}{a} \sinh a(x+c)$$

where a is given in equation 3 section 1.2.

Applying the boundary conditions Fig. 6b gives

$$\sigma_p(x) = -\sigma_p \frac{\sinh ax}{\sinh aL/2}$$

Finally, summing with σ_p , the uniform stress, gives equation 1 and differentiating with respect to x gives $\tau(x)$ equation 2.